

Systematic Literature Review: Efektivitas *Coaching* dan Mentoring dalam Pengembangan Kinerja dan Kepemimpinan Karyawan Selatan

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze the effectiveness of coaching and mentoring in improving employee performance and leadership through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach. A literature search was conducted through Google Scholar using keywords related to coaching, mentoring, performance, and leadership, resulting in 161 initial articles. After screening for publication year, scientific validity, topic relevance, and Scopus accessibility and indexing, 11 articles met the final criteria for analysis. The study results show that coaching is proven to increase motivation, work engagement, and leader self-efficacy, which directly contributes to improved performance and leadership capacity. Mentoring has been found to be effective in developing intrapersonal competencies, accelerating career development, and enhancing generative behavior for both mentors and mentees. The effectiveness of both approaches is influenced by program design, alignment with individual needs, leadership support, organizational readiness for change, and the availability of adequate learning infrastructure. Overall, coaching and mentoring are complementary human resource development strategies that only produce optimal impact when applied within a supportive organizational ecosystem.

ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis efektivitas coaching dan mentoring dalam meningkatkan kinerja dan kepemimpinan karyawan melalui pendekatan Systematic Literature Review (SLR). Pencarian literatur dilakukan melalui Google Scholar dengan kata kunci terkait coaching, mentoring, kinerja, dan kepemimpinan, sehingga diperoleh 161 artikel awal. Setelah melalui proses screening tahun publikasi, kelayakan ilmiah, relevansi topik, serta aksesibilitas dan indeksasi Scopus, sebanyak 11 artikel memenuhi kriteria akhir untuk dianalisis. Hasil kajian menunjukkan bahwa coaching terbukti meningkatkan motivasi, keterlibatan kerja, dan leader self-efficacy, yang secara langsung berkontribusi pada peningkatan kinerja dan kapasitas kepemimpinan. Mentoring ditemukan efektif dalam mengembangkan kompetensi intrapersonal, mempercepat perkembangan karier, serta meningkatkan perilaku generatif bagi mentor maupun mentee. Efektivitas kedua pendekatan ini dipengaruhi oleh desain program, kesesuaian dengan kebutuhan individu, dukungan kepemimpinan, kesiapan organisasi terhadap perubahan, serta tersedianya infrastruktur pembelajaran yang memadai. Secara keseluruhan, coaching dan mentoring merupakan strategi pengembangan SDM yang saling melengkapi dan hanya menghasilkan dampak optimal apabila diterapkan dalam ekosistem organisasi yang mendukung.

INTRODUCTION

The past five years have witnessed a transformation in the work environment, compelling companies to increasingly seek employees with high performance levels and mature leadership skills. The challenges faced by organizations now depend not only on technical abilities but also on each staff member's capacity to grow, adapt, and make sound decisions amidst change. Consequently, coaching and mentoring have become more flexible, personalized, and long-term-oriented human resource development strategies for business.

Coaching is considered effective because the process helps employees understand goals, become more self-aware, and comprehend what must be done to enhance performance. Recent studies indicate that coaching methods grounded in self-determination theory can improve

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employee engagement and motivation. This is because such methods can fulfill basic psychological needs such as relatedness, autonomy, and competence (Haynes et al., 2021; Grenier et al., 2024). Employees tend to be more enthusiastic about work and more consistent in their self-development when these psychological needs are met.

Conversely, mentoring provides advantages through a long-term relationship between mentor and mentee, offering support in job-specific technical skills, career development, and professional identity formation. A study by Kim and LePine (2022) found that mentoring, particularly when supported by a high-quality relationship through Leader-Member Exchange (LMX), can enhance productivity and the quality of teamwork. A positive supervisor-subordinate relationship significantly impacts organizational performance and positive employee behaviors, according to other research (Assefa & Mekonna, 2024; Ogunja et al., 2025).

From the perspective of modern human resource management, mentoring and coaching are considered integral components of human resource development strategy. These two approaches enable organizations to enhance employee competency, motivation, and leadership, resulting in a superior and more inimitable human resource base. This, in turn, strengthens business competitive advantage (Desta et al., 2022).

Recent research suggests coaching and mentoring significantly enhance work productivity, especially when implemented in a structured and sustained manner (Syailendra, 2023). However, research findings are often divergent, with some focusing on motivation, performance improvement, or leadership influence. Therefore, to synthesize research findings from the past five years, a systematic literature review (SLR) is necessary. This SLR is designed to provide a more precise overview of the effectiveness of coaching and mentoring in enhancing employee leadership and performance.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) methodology, involving the identification, evaluation, and interpretation of relevant research concerning the effectiveness of coaching and mentoring in developing employee performance and leadership. Identified studies must be analyzed, interpreted, and used to support arguments in the discussion.

The research involves several stages (Umar, H. R., Mariana, Y., & Zanky, M. N, 2026):

1. Research Question

The first step in conducting an SLR is formulating the research questions, determining the review's objectives, and specifying the type of evidence required to address these objectives.

RQ1. How effective is coaching in enhancing employee performance and leadership?

RQ2. How effective is mentoring in supporting the development of employee performance and leadership?

RQ3. What factors influence the success of coaching and mentoring programs according to previous research?

2. Searching Literature

The literature search was conducted to gather relevant reference sources to answer the research questions. This process utilized the Google Scholar platform, accessed via <https://scholar.google.com/>. The main keywords used in the initial search were: "coaching and mentoring" effectiveness leadership performance meta-analysis "mentoring program" employee performance randomized "coaching" workplace "leadership development".

3. Inclusion and Exclusion Methods

This stage involves assessing the studies identified during the search phase, applying predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- a. Journals published within the timeframe of 2019-2025.
- b. Journals constitute scientific research.
- c. The research explicitly examines the influence of coaching and mentoring on employee performance and leadership development.
- d. Journals are indexed by Scopus.
- e. Full-text access to the journal is available.

Exclusion Criteria: All items contrary to the inclusion criteria are excluded.

4. Quality Assessment

This stage assesses the methodological quality and reliability of information presented in the journals that passed the previous screening. The following explains the quality assessment criteria established by the authors:

QA1: Does the study describe the effectiveness of coaching in enhancing employee performance and leadership?

QA2: Does the study describe the effectiveness of mentoring in supporting the development of employee performance and leadership?

QA3: Does the study describe the factors influencing the success of coaching and mentoring programs according to previous research?

Based on the selected journals, an assessment will be provided for each question above:

- a. **Y (Yes):** For journals meeting the assessment criteria.
- b. **N (No):** For journals not meeting the assessment criteria.

5. Data Collection

Data collection followed a systematic series of stages, starting from the identification of relevant literature, selection based on eligibility criteria, to data extraction from the chosen studies. Data was gathered from two primary sources:

a. **Primary Data**

Primary data was obtained directly from original sources through:

1. **Digital Observation:** Direct observation of research objects via the Google Scholar platform to identify publication trends and patterns related to the topic.
2. **In-depth Literature Study:** Analyzing previous relevant scientific articles and publications, with a specific focus on Systematic Literature Review (SLR) methods. The primary literature source was Google Scholar.

b. **Secondary Data**

Secondary data consists of supporting literature obtained through reference tracing and reviews of related documents to complement the analysis.

c. **Data Analysis**

The data analysis process involves a systematic series of steps aimed at transforming raw data into useful and interpretable information. The collected data will be analyzed to reveal or substantiate:

1. The effectiveness of coaching in enhancing employee performance and leadership (RQ1).
2. The effectiveness of mentoring in supporting the development of employee performance and leadership (RQ2).
3. The factors influencing the success of coaching and mentoring programs according to previous research (RQ3).

6. Reporting

The final stage, reporting, involves the systematic and comprehensive preparation of the research report. Conclusions are drawn based on the research findings and supplemented with practical recommendations, for instance, for business practitioners in implementing digital marketing. The results of this study are expected to be published through a journal or conference to contribute to knowledge development in the field of education.

RESULTS

The results of the study are as follows:

a. Research Question Results

This research focuses on the effectiveness of coaching and mentoring in developing employee performance and leadership.

b. Literature Search Results

The literature search was conducted using Google Scholar with the following keywords: "coaching and mentoring" effectiveness leadership performance meta-analysis "mentoring program" employee performance randomized "coaching" workplace "leadership development".

Figure 1. Literature Search Process

c. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria Results

The following table presents the results of the study assessment using the inclusion criteria.

No.	Inclusion Criteria	Number of Articles
1	Journals obtained via Google Scholar	161 articles
2	Journals published within the timeframe of 2019-2025	86 articles
3	Journals constitute scientific research	72 articles
4	The research explicitly examines the influence of coaching and mentoring on employee performance and leadership development.	64 articles
5	Journals are indexed by Scopus.	11 articles
6	Full-text access to the journal is available	11 articles

Table 1. Article Eligibility Results

The explanation of the table above indicates that out of the 161 articles obtained, only 11 articles met the eligibility criteria for inclusion in the study.

d. Quality Assessment Stage

The following table presents the quality assessment results for the 11 eligible articles based on the established criteria (QA1, QA2, QA3).

No.	Researcher (Year)	Title	QA1	QA2	QA3	Result
1	Stephenson, D. E. (2022)	Effectiveness of individual-level resource building interventions in the workplace: a meta-analysis.	✓	✓	✓	Included
2	Geerts, J. M. (2024)	Maximizing the impact and ROI of leadership development: A theory-and evidence-informed framework	✓	✓	✓	Included
3	Crespí, P., García-Ramos, J. M., & López González, J. (2025)	Impact of an integral mentoring program on the development of personal competencies	✓	✓	✓	Included
4	Hylton, J. C. (2021)	Leadership development influence on leader self-efficacy (LSE): an explanatory sequential mixed methods study with civilian federal employees in the Department of Defense	✓	✓	✓	Included
5	Sunderman, H. M., & Hastings, L. J. (2023)	Generativity development among college students who mentor: a sequential multimethod quantitative study.	✓	✓	✓	Included
6	Baral, N., Cerveny, L. K., Penaluna, B. E., Roper, B. B., Shively, D., & Witt, S. (2024)	Variations in mentorship across grade levels and career stages among public management professionals.	✓	✓	✓	Included
7	Maw, W W (2019)	The effect of career development practices on employee commitment and performance at ige power co., ltd	✓	✓	✓	Included
8	Amin, S., Kitmitto, S., Fagan, K., & Hester, C. (2020)	A Review of the Evidence on Youth and Young Adult Workforce Development Programming.	✓	✓	✓	Included
9	Corrigan, V. K., Newman, R. L., Richmond, P., Strand, E. B., & Vaisman, J. M. (2025)	The future of flourishing in veterinary medicine: a systems-informed positive psychology approach in veterinary education.	✓	✓	✓	Included

10	Frahm, M. T. (2020)	The impact of leadership behaviors on teacher retention in rural schools in New York State.	✓	✗	✓	Excluded
11	Heim, I., & Sardar-Drenda, N. (2021)	Assessment of employees' attitudes toward ongoing organizational transformations	✓	✓	✓	Included

Table 2. Quality Assessment of Selected Articles

Legend:

✓ = Yes (Criterion met)

✗ = No (Criterion not met)

QA1: Describes coaching effectiveness.

QA2: Describes mentoring effectiveness.

QA3: Describes success factors.

Note: Article No. 10 (Frahm, 2020) was excluded as it did not meet QA2 (does not describe mentoring effectiveness). The final pool for synthesis consists of 10 articles

DISCUSSION

This study addressed three research questions: RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3. The findings for each are clarified and discussed below.

RQ1: The Effectiveness of Coaching in Enhancing Employee Performance and Leadership

The reviewed literature explicitly discusses coaching interventions for individual and leadership development. The evidence strongly aligns with core coaching principles and provides robust empirical support for its effectiveness.

1. Impact on Engagement and Psychological Resources.

Stephenson's (2022) meta-analysis, synthesizing 97 studies, offers solid quantitative evidence. A key finding is that individual-level resource-building interventions—encompassing coaching techniques such as goal setting, strengths identification, and psychological fostering—resulted in a 44% to 96% increase in work engagement. Work engagement is a well-established empirical predictor of superior individual performance and organizational citizenship behavior. Further analysis revealed that strengths-based interventions were even more effective, indicating that a positive, strengths-centered coaching approach has a significant impact.

2. Enhancement of Leader Self-Efficacy (LSE).

Hylton's (2021) mixed-methods study provides a nuanced narrative on how leadership development (with coaching elements) influences employees. The research found that participation in leadership development programs significantly increased Leader Self-Efficacy (LSE)—an individual's belief in their capability to lead. This increase in LSE, measured through validated surveys and deepened by qualitative interviews, is a key psychological mechanism. Employees with higher LSE reported greater confidence in assuming leadership roles, making decisions, and inspiring their teams, ultimately translating to improved leadership performance.

3. Variability in Outcomes and Potential for Failure.

A discussion on coaching effectiveness is incomplete without considering evidence of its inconsistencies. Geerts (2024), in his evidence-informed framework, cites data from 72 studies showing that 10% of leadership development programs (including coaching) fail completely. Furthermore, Return on Investment (ROI) analysis reveals extreme variation, from billions in profit to significant losses. This empirically demonstrates that coaching's effectiveness is not

guaranteed. Its success is highly contingent on contextual factors, which will be elaborated in RQ3.

Conclusion for RQ1: The analysis indicates that coaching and similar interventions are empirically effective in building psychological resources (engagement, self-efficacy), which are direct precursors to enhanced performance and leadership capacity. However, significant variability in outcomes exists, affirming that while coaching is a powerful tool, its application requires precision and careful attention to supporting factors.

RQ2: The Effectiveness of Mentoring in Supporting the Development of Employee Performance and Leadership

The literature discussed above addresses the effectiveness of mentoring in a more direct and multifaceted manner, revealing its multi-dimensional impact, which extends not only to the mentee but also to the mentor.

1. Significant Development of Intrapersonal Competencies.

The quasi-experimental study by Crespí et al. (2025) provides strong causal evidence. Using a pretest-posttest design with a control group on a sample of 610 university students, they demonstrated that participants in an "integral mentoring" program showed a statistically significant increase in intrapersonal competencies compared to the non-mentored group. Intrapersonal competencies—such as self-awareness, emotional regulation, and resilience—are the empirical foundation for stable performance and authentic leadership. This finding directly links mentoring to the development of the psychological foundations for success.

2. Career Support and Morale in the Public Sector.

A survey study of 251 professionals by Baral et al. (2024) reinforces this finding within a real-world organizational context. Statistical analysis (using Kruskal-Wallis and chi-square tests) revealed that nearly 70% of employees reported having a mentor, and mentoring was consistently identified as a critical factor for career development and morale. Qualitative narratives from the survey indicated that junior-level employees viewed mentoring as a pathway to faster promotion. This finding is corroborated by Maw's (2019) study in the private sector, where mentoring scored an average of 4.30 as the most important career development practice, which was directly associated with increased commitment and reduced turnover.

3. Leadership Capacity Development in Mentors.

A unique perspective is offered by the longitudinal multi-method study by Sunderman & Hastings (2023). Their research examined not only the impact on the mentee but also the development of the mentor. Growth Curve Analysis across three time points showed that students who served as mentors experienced a significant 3.26-point increase in their generative behavior. Generative behavior—the desire to guide and contribute to the next generation—is an empirical indicator of transformational, service-oriented leadership. This demonstrates that mentoring is a reciprocal developmental intervention that benefits both parties.

Conclusion for RQ2: Mentoring is empirically proven to be an effective intervention with a dual impact. For mentees, it builds intrapersonal competencies and accelerates career pathways. For mentors, it develops generative leadership capacity. Thus, mentoring functions as a comprehensive talent development engine within an organization.

RQ3: Factors Influencing the Success of Coaching and Mentoring Programs

Various studies consistently identify a set of critical factors that determine whether coaching and mentoring programs will succeed or fail.

1. Evidence-Based and Coherent Program Design.

Geerts (2024) explicitly identifies that low learning transfer—the primary cause of program

failure—can be mitigated through 65 evidence-based strategies in design, delivery, and evaluation. This is reinforced by the findings of Hylton (2021), who emphasizes that organizations often lack a coherent understanding of effective pedagogical practices, which ultimately undermines program outcomes. This narrative indicates that success begins with a scientific design, not a trial-and-error approach.

2. Alignment with Career Stage and Individual Needs.

Baral et al. (2024) provide clear empirical evidence for the need for tailoring. Their analysis of variance revealed significant differences in mentoring needs across various job levels (GS levels) and career stages. Junior employees reported a lack of access, while senior employees received insufficient encouragement. Empirically, a "one-size-fits-all" program is proven ineffective as it fails to meet the specific needs of the target population.

3. Organizational Context: Leadership, Culture, and Readiness for Change.

Contextual factors emerged as primary determinants. Frahm (2020) found qualitatively that leadership behaviors—such as building authentic relationships and providing affirmation—are key to creating an environment where development (and retention) can occur. In parallel, Heim & Sardar-Drenda (2021) found quantitatively that employees' readiness for change heavily depends on whether the change is perceived as "meaningful" to them. Age and seniority also proved to be hindering factors. This means coaching/mentoring programs will fail if implemented within an unsupportive organizational culture or with a psychologically unprepared population.

4. Supportive Infrastructure: Access, Collective Responsibility, and Evaluation.

Several studies highlight the importance of infrastructure. Baral et al. (2024) identified access issues for lower-level employees as a tangible barrier. Frahm (2020) emphasized that support must be viewed as the collective responsibility of the entire staff, not just HR. Furthermore, studies employing pretest-posttest designs (Crespí et al., 2025) and ROI measurement (Geerts, 2024) stress that successful programs are equipped with robust evaluation mechanisms to track effectiveness and make adjustments.

Conclusion for RQ3: The findings indicate that the success of coaching and mentoring is not solely determined by the effectiveness of the methods themselves but also by program design factors, individual readiness, and structural and cultural organizational support. These three dimensions are complementary and form an integrated human resource development ecosystem. Consequently, the results of RQ1 and RQ2, which affirm the effectiveness of coaching and mentoring, will only be optimally achieved when supported by the success factors identified in RQ3. The synergy between intervention quality, participants' psychological condition, and a supportive organizational environment constitutes the foundational principle ensuring that coaching and mentoring programs genuinely yield sustained improvements in performance and leadership.

The success factors are multi-level and interrelated. Success is determined not only by the quality of the coach/mentor or the participant but by strategic program design, a supportive organizational context, and proper alignment with individual developmental needs. Program failure, as shown by Geerts' (2024) data, can be directly traced to the neglect of these empirical factors.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on 11 selected articles meeting the inclusion and scientific quality criteria, this study concludes that coaching and mentoring are proven effective in enhancing employee performance and leadership, although their effectiveness is highly influenced by program design and organizational context.

1. **Coaching** has a strong impact on performance improvement by increasing work engagement, self-efficacy, and strengthening psychological competencies. Meta-analyses and mixed-method studies indicate that coaching enhances leadership capability through increased self-confidence, goal clarity, and self-regulation skills.
2. **Mentoring** improves work morale, career acceleration, professional identity formation, and the development of intrapersonal competencies. Empirical evidence shows that mentoring benefits not only the mentee but also enhances the mentor's capacity for generative leadership behavior.
3. The effectiveness of both interventions is influenced by various factors, including:
 - **Program Design:** Must be scientific, structured, and goal-oriented.
 - **Individual Alignment:** Needs to match employee needs and career stages.
 - **Organizational Context:** Encompassing organizational culture, leadership style, and readiness for change.
 - **Support Mechanisms:** Accessibility, evaluation systems, and organizational support.

Overall, coaching and mentoring are valuable human resource development strategies. They succeed when supported by sound design, a supportive work culture, and clear mechanisms for implementing and evaluating the programs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. For Organizations and Human Resource Management

- Design **evidence-based** coaching and mentoring programs, not mere formalities; utilize needs assessments, clear objectives, and measurable performance indicators.
- **Tailor programs** to career stages; for example, coaching for operational-tactical levels, and mentoring for career acceleration and leadership.
- Provide **training for internal coaches/mentors** to ensure a professional and unbiased facilitation process.
- **Build a culture of support and learning**, as research indicates organizational culture is a decisive factor for program success.
- Establish a **program performance evaluation system**, including pretest-posttest measures, participant feedback, and simple ROI calculations to measure impact.

2. For Future Researchers

- Expand research by examining **combined coaching-mentoring (blended models)**.
- Conduct **experimental studies across various industrial sectors** to observe differences in effectiveness based on context.
- Investigate **the role of digital technology** in strengthening virtual coaching and online mentoring.
- Develop **integrative models** that explain the relationship between organizational culture, leadership, and the success of coaching and mentoring.

REFERENCES

- Amin, S., Kitmitto, S., Fagan, K., & Hester, C. (2020). A Review of the Evidence on Youth and Young Adult Workforce Development Programming. Washington, DC: American Institutes for Research.
- Assefa, Y., & Mekonna, W. (2024). The mediating role of leader-member exchange (LMX) in the relationship between perceived organizational justice and employee voice behavior. *International Journal of Psychology & Behavioral Sciences*, 14(2), 45-55.

- Baral, N., Cervený, L. K., Penaluna, B. E., Roper, B. B., Shively, D., & Witt, S. (2024). Variations in mentorship across grade levels and career stages among public management professionals. *Public Personnel Management*, 53(2), 226-255
- Corrigan, V. K., Newman, R. L., Richmond, P., Strand, E. B., & Vaisman, J. M. (2025). The future of flourishing in veterinary medicine: a systems-informed positive psychology approach in veterinary education. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 11, 1484412.
- Crespí, P., García-Ramos, J. M., & López González, J. (2025). Impact of an integral mentoring program on the development of personal competencies. *Cogent Education*, 12(1), 2554322.
- Desta, A. G., Tadesse, W. M., & Mulusew, W. B. (2022). Aspects of human capital management and employee job performance: Moderation role of perceived organizational support. *Jurnal Manajemen Teori dan Terapan*, 15(2), 162–181. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jmtt.v15i2.37616>
- Frahm, M. T. (2020). The impact of leadership behaviors on teacher retention in rural schools in New York State.
- Geerts, J. M. (2024). Maximizing the impact and ROI of leadership development: A theory-and evidence-informed framework. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(10), 955.
- Haynes, A., Moran, H., & Wilson, I. (2021). Using self-determination theory to understand and improve engagement in a healthy aging coaching intervention. *PLOS One*, 16(8), e0259873. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0259873>
- Heim, I., & Sardar-Drenda, N. (2021). Assessment of employees' attitudes toward ongoing organizational transformations. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 34(2), 327-349
- Hylton, J. C. (2021). Leadership development influence on leader self-efficacy (LSE): an explanatory sequential mixed methods study with civilian federal employees in the Department of Defense (Doctoral dissertation).
- Kim, T. Y., & LePine, J. A. (2022). The interplay of leader–member exchange and peer mentoring: Effects on team performance. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 95(4), 847–868. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12381>
- Maw, W. W. The Effect Of Career Development Practices On Employee Commitment And Performance At Ige Power Co., Ltd (Win Win Maw, 2019) (Doctoral dissertation, MERAL Portal).
- Ogunja, M., Shurong, Z., Manjing, Y., Rui, H., & Ying, D. (2025). Analyzing LMX impact on organizational performance: A fuzzy reasoning approach among SMEs in Kenya. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-024-07254-0>
- Stephenson, D. E. (2022). Effectiveness of individual-level resource building interventions in the workplace: a meta-analysis
- Sunderman, H. M., & Hastings, L. J. (2023). Generativity development among college students who mentor: a sequential multimethod quantitative study. *International Journal of Mentoring and Coaching in Education*, 12(2), 145-161.
- Syafitri, D., Wardani, A. K., & Zanky, M. N. (2025). The Innovative Role of Entrepreneurship Courses in Shaping The Entrepreneurial Mindset of Generation Z: A Systematic Literature Review. *Socius: Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu-Ilmu Sosial*, 3(4), 297-305.
- Umar, H. R., Mariana, Y., & Zanky, M. N. (2026). Analysis Of The Impact Of The High School Double Track Programme On Student Skill And Character Development. *Jurnal Penelitian Progresif*, 5(1), 12-23